

ELEMENTARY TEACHERS' READINESS AND RESPONSE STRATEGIES IN THE FACE OF NATURAL DISASTERS: A COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) is a critical global priority, particularly in regions highly vulnerable to natural hazards. This descriptive-correlational study assessed the disaster readiness and response strategies of 107 elementary teachers in Hinabangan I and II Districts, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2024-2025. Findings revealed that while teachers generally exhibit strong preparedness for DRRM drills, emergency evacuation, and emergency response, their overall readiness is only weakly correlated with factors like age, teaching experience, and disaster exposure, despite an overwhelmingly positive attitude towards DRRM. Significant challenges persist in financial resources and technology, alongside moderate issues with manpower and technical knowledge. Although teachers endorse various response strategies, a weak positive correlation exists between their attitude towards DRRM and their actual response. Crucially, a moderate correlation was found between readiness in emergency evacuation and response skills, and actual disaster response. These insights underscore the need for targeted, tiered DRRM training, enhanced drill realism, improved resource mobilization, and a holistic approach to preparedness to strengthen teacher capabilities and ensure resilient school communities.

Keywords: *Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM), Disaster Preparedness, Response Strategies, Elementary Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Nature has both gentle and aggressive side. The gentle side offers peace and serenity, while the aggressive side shows fierceness and ferociousness. As a result, the gentle side of nature is loved, while the aggressive side is feared due to the devastations that happen. The forces of nature, such as the movement of the air, water, and land, cannot be controlled by humans. Hence, the occurrence of natural hazards, such as storms, earthquake, and floods are inevitable. When the calamitous situation arises, people cannot control them, but they can prevent them and mitigate their impact through disaster preparedness measures and response strategies. Since natural disasters are unpredictable, the disaster preparedness effort of a teacher may be compromised and therefore, there is a need to assess their level of readiness. Correspondingly, the teachers' response strategies may also be compromised with the severity of the natural disasters. Hence, it is likewise necessary to assess their response strategies in the face of natural disasters, and considering the challenges that they may be encountering.

As emphasized by Kekic and Milenkovic (2019), disaster risk reduction begins in schools, underscoring the vital role of education in building disaster resilience by minimizing the vulnerabilities of the population. In this context, the integration of disaster risk reduction (DRR) into the educational system should be recognized as an effective risk reduction strategy, with teachers' preparedness and response capacities serving as its foundation. However, evidence suggests that these capacities remain insufficient in practice. A UNESCO survey conducted across 30 countries before and after 2014 revealed that the response dimension among teachers largely focused on basic familiarization with early warning signs and hazard signals, evacuation or sheltering procedures, drills and exercises, fundamental first aid, health and safety measures, and general guidance on staying safe after a hazard has passed. Despite these efforts, inadequacies in teachers' response capacities persist, indicating the need for more comprehensive and sustained capacity-building initiatives in disaster preparedness and response (Masocha et al., 2025).

Lloyd et al. (2022) emphasize that the Philippines experiences compounded disaster risks due to its geographic exposure to multiple hazards and pervasive social vulnerabilities that intensify the impacts of natural events. The World Risk Index of 2014 showed that the country was second in terms of exposure and risks to natural disasters. Similarly, the Global Risk Index in 2015 ranked the country as the most affected country by natural disasters in 2013; and the World Vision report in 2017 showed that due to the regular occurrence of typhoons, existence of tectonic faults, and presence of several active volcanoes, the country ranked third as the most disaster-prone country in the world. In the 2022 World Risk Index, the country was already in number one spot for the most disaster-prone country in the world, with the index score of 46.86, which was the highest among the top ten most disaster-prone countries worldwide because of high risk, exposure, and vulnerability to natural disasters. The occurrence of an average of 20 typhoons that enter the Philippine Area of Responsibility (PAR) annually, with the most intense between July and October, makes the country at high risk and vulnerability to damaging floods and landslides. More so, other reasons for the country's vulnerability

and high risk to natural disasters are its location in the ring and fire and typhoon belt in the Pacific Ocean (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, 2023).

The educational institutions are not spared from the occurrence of natural disasters. These institutions must also be given careful consideration in disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) planning efforts because they are likewise significantly impacted by natural disasters. Natural disasters affect the students' study schedules and lower the standard of instruction provided because of the disruption of classes. Additionally, when school buildings are used as places for evacuation, students and teachers are relocated and left without a place to hold classes, and worse, school facilities are occasionally damaged due to evacuees' abuse, especially the restroom and washing facilities. In fact, from the School Year 2009-2010 to School Year 2017-2018, 42,810 schools nationwide were damaged due to natural hazards. Hence, these natural hazards impede the provision of education and threaten and affect both the lives of students and teachers, and ruin other educational resources and investments (DepEd, 2020).

Consequently, the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010, also known as the Republic Act Number 101211, enacted the multisectoral management of disasters. This act established a comprehensive National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan (NDRRMP) as a state policy, with the goal of strengthening the ability of national and local government to create disaster resilience and institutionalize arrangements and measures for reducing disaster risks. The multisectoral approach to disaster management by the government refers to the collaborative process between and involvement of multiple sectors, including governmental and non-governmental organizations, the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and the academia, in the country's effort to manage multifaceted disaster risks. This approach is also described as reciprocal, with the different sectors feeding knowledge and learnings into the processes used by the government thereby influencing and informing its disaster risk reduction and management planning. In turn, the country's processes will inform and guide the multiple sectors in managing risks (DILG, 2024).

The academia, as one of the sectors mandated to collaborate in disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM), plays a crucial role in all phases of disaster cycle, from prevention to post-recovery management. As an educational institution, the schools are, by necessity, involved in DRRM with the mission of contributing broadly to society. The teachers are particularly expected to play a pivotal role in disaster preparedness that refers to the systematic process of using administrative measures and operational skills to implement strategies and policies, and improve coping capacities in order to lessen the adverse impacts of hazards to minimize the opportunity for development of disasters. These teachers are also expected to contribute to response management in the face of natural disasters, which refers to the stage where there is an immediate action to limit the hazards created by the disaster (Izumi, 2016).

However, educational institutions, specifically the teachers, face challenges in their

efforts to contribute to response management to natural disasters because of their limitations in mobilizing funds, technology and equipment, manpower, and technical knowledge and understanding. Considering these limitations, teachers can offer assistance only with respect to the aspects of disaster preparation and response management that they are capable of providing. These dilemma raises the question of the teachers' capacity to extend assistance in the preparation and response to natural disasters especially in schools located in a province with a high risk of vulnerability to these disasters. The Province of Samar is included in the list of top 20 provinces in the Philippines highly at risk to the occurrence of natural disasters, such as typhoons and combined climate- and weather-related risks. In fact, the Municipality of Basey and Municipality of Marabut were greatly affected by the 2013 Super Typhoon Yolanda. On December 6, 2014, the Municipality of Daram was greatly affected by Typhoon Ruby, and one of the barangays in the City of Catbalogan had faced the wrath of landslide on December 30, 2014 (ADRC, 2015).

Amidst this challenging backdrop, a consistent pattern in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) implementation has been observed across all 21 schools in Hinabangan I and II Districts spanning School Year 2022-2023 (Quarters 3 & 4), School Year 2023-2024 (Quarters 3 & 4), and School Year 2024-2025 (Quarters 1 & 2). In each of these periods, every school (100%) commendably executed "Duck, Cover, and Hold" drills, establishing a solid foundation for immediate safety protocols. However, this consistent strength in initial response is consistently undermined by critical, recurring gaps in comprehensive disaster readiness.

Notably, a persistent concern is the failure of two schools (19 schools or 90.48%) to conduct evacuation drills across all reported quarters. This is a vital omission, as orderly evacuation is fundamental for ensuring the safe and efficient movement of students and personnel during actual emergencies. Furthermore, a significant and unchanging gap exists in the crucial post-activity phase: in every reported quarter across all three school years, only 16 schools or 76.19 percent engaged in tabletop and functional exercises. These exercises are not mere formalities; they are indispensable for debriefing, pinpointing weaknesses in current plans, refining response strategies, and building the adaptive capacity teachers need to act effectively under pressure. The consistent neglect of these components across multiple school years and quarters indicates a deeply entrenched systemic challenge requiring urgent intervention (Division Consolidated Report on the Conduct of Earthquake and Fire Drill, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025).

Adding to these enduring issues, observations from Fiscal Year 2025, Quarter 2, during actual drill conduct, illuminate several common operational challenges. These include limited equipment, which can severely hamper effective response efforts; a concerning lack of seriousness and proper behavior among learners, suggesting a need for deeper engagement and understanding of the drills' purpose; and instances of improper practice of "Duck, Cover, and Hold", indicating that despite high participation, the quality of initial instruction and reinforcement may be lacking. Finally, limited attendance of learners during drills and limited participation from Barangay Local

Government Unit (BLGU) and Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) officers highlight a broader challenge in fostering robust community and stakeholder engagement, which is critical for holistic and sustainable school-based DRRM. Collectively, these findings reveal that while initial compliance with basic safety procedures is high, crucial elements of advanced drill execution, post-drill analysis, and vital community involvement remain consistently underdeveloped, posing a significant risk to comprehensive disaster preparedness in the district (Division Consolidated Report on the Conduct of Q2 Earthquake and Fire Drill, 2025).

With these predicaments, this study was conducted to assess the level of readiness and response strategies in the face of natural disasters in elementary schools in the Districts of Hinabangan I and II, Schools Division of Samar. This research provided a research-based data on the need for upskilling and reskilling of teachers on disaster preparedness and response strategies.

Research Questions

This study assessed the readiness and response strategies in the face of natural disasters of elementary teachers in the Districts of Hinabangan I and II, Schools Division of Samar, during the School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 teaching position;
 - 1.6 grade level taught;
 - 1.7 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.8 relevant in-service trainings;
 - 1.9 number of School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (SDDRM) activities attended or participated;
 - 1.10 types of natural disasters experienced;
 - 1.11 frequency of exposure to natural disasters; and
 - 1.12 attitude toward disaster risk reduction and management?
2. What is the level of readiness to natural disasters of teacher-respondents in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 2.1 disaster risk reduction and management drill;
 - 2.2 emergency evacuation; and
 - 2.3 emergency response?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of readiness to natural disasters of teacher-respondents and each of their profile variates?
4. What are the response strategies used by the teacher-respondents in the face of natural disasters along the following parameters:
 - 4.1 immediate response strategies;

- 4.2 short-term response strategies; and
- 4.3 protracted duration response strategies?
- 5. Is there a significant relationship between the response strategies used by the teacher-respondents in the face of natural disasters and the following variates:
 - 5.1 teacher-related variates; and
 - 5.2 level of readiness to natural disasters?
- 6. What are the challenges encountered by the teacher-respondents as they prepare for natural disasters along the following domains:
 - 6.1 financial resources;
 - 6.2 technology and equipment;
 - 6.3 manpower; and
 - 6.4 technical knowledge and understanding?
- 7. What intervention program may be developed based on the findings of this study?

Locale of the Study

Figure 1 presents the map of the locale of the study, the public elementary schools in the Districts of Hinabangan I and II, Schools Division of Samar.

Figure 1

METHODOLC

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the readiness and response strategies of elementary teachers in the Districts of Hinabangan I and II, Schools Division of Samar, in the face of natural disasters. A total of 107 teachers from all public elementary schools in the two districts participated, using complete enumeration to ensure comprehensive representation. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire consisting of five parts: (1) teacher profile; (2) attitude toward disaster risk reduction and management; (3) level of readiness in disaster drills, emergency evacuation, and response; (4) response strategies across immediate, short-term, and protracted durations; and (5) challenges encountered in preparation for disasters. The questionnaire items were adapted from validated studies and reviewed by experts for content validity. Data gathering was conducted personally by the researcher over two weeks, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity. Descriptive statistics, including Frequency Count, Percentage, Mean, Median, Mean Absolute Deviation, and Weighted Mean, were used to summarize the data, while Point-biserial correlation, Eta correlation, Cramer's V, and Spearman's rho were employed to determine relationships between teacher profiles, readiness levels, and response strategies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The age distribution of the teacher-respondents reveals a bimodal pattern, with the largest groups falling within the 27 to 31 year old and 42 to 46 year old ranges, both comprising 22.43% of the total respondents. The mean age of the teachers is approximately 38.93 years, closely mirrored by the median age of 38.00 years, indicating a relatively symmetrical age distribution. The mean absolute deviation of 6.9713 years suggests a moderate level of variability in the ages around the mean. Furthermore, there is a significant gender imbalance among the respondents, with a considerably higher number of female teachers (88) compared to male teachers (19).

2. A significant portion of the teacher-respondents, nearly half at 47.66%, reported a gross monthly family income within the range of 30,000 to 34,999. This indicates that this income bracket represents the most common financial situation among the surveyed teachers.

3. The civil status of the teacher-respondents indicates that the vast majority, 73.83%, are married. Following this, a notable proportion, 25.23%, are single. A very small fraction of the respondents, just 0.93%, reported being widowed.

4. The data on the highest educational attainment of the teacher-respondents reveals that the largest group, comprising 35.51%, have completed some units in graduate programs. This is closely followed by teachers who have pursued further studies with units in post-graduate programs, representing 23.36% of the respondents.

5. The professional positions held by the teacher-respondents show that the majority, a substantial 66.36%, are Teacher III. The next largest group is comprised of Teacher I, accounting for 17.76% of the respondents.

6. The grade levels handled by the teacher-respondents indicate that the largest proportion, 16.82%, are currently teaching Grade 3. Following closely behind are teachers handling Kindergarten level at 15.89%, and then those teaching Grade 1 at 14.95%.

7. The teaching experience among the respondents shows that the largest group, 27.10%, have been teaching for 6 to 10 years. This is closely followed by teachers with 11 to 15 years of experience, making up 26.17% of the respondents. A notable portion, 23.36%, have relatively less experience, teaching for less than 1 to 5 years. This distribution indicates that the majority of the surveyed teachers have accumulated a moderate amount of teaching experience, with a substantial number also in the early stages of their careers.

8. The frequency of relevant school level training attended by the teacher-respondents has a weighted mean of 3.28, indicating that such training is often attended. District level training has a weighted mean of 2.51, also suggesting it is often attended. In contrast, division level training, with a weighted mean of 1.88, is attended sometimes. Regional level training, with a weighted mean of 1.41, and national level training, with a weighted mean of 1.23, are both reported as never attended by the majority of the teacher-respondents.

9. The number of School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (SDRRM) activities attended or participated in by the teacher-respondents reveals a notable concentration at two levels. A substantial majority, 48.60%, have attended or participated in 4 to 6 SDRRM activities, while an equal proportion, another 48.60%, have attended or participated in less than 1 to 3 activities. This indicates a notable split in the level of engagement with SDRRM activities among the surveyed teachers, with large groups at both moderate and lower levels of participation.

10. The experience of natural disasters among the teacher-respondents shows that the most common combination reported, by 28.97% of teachers, includes flood, storm, and earthquake. Following this, 21.50% of teachers experienced both storm and earthquake. Another notable group, comprising 14.02% of the respondents, reported experiencing a combination of flood, storm, earthquake, and landslide. This indicates that a significant portion of the surveyed teachers have faced multiple types of natural disasters in their experience.

11. The frequency of exposure to natural disasters among the teacher-respondents reveals that the vast majority, 60.75%, have experienced such events 4 to 6 times. A smaller but still notable proportion, 38.32%, reported a frequency of less than 1 to 3 times. This suggests that a significant number of the surveyed teachers have had repeated experiences with natural disasters.

12. The overall attitude of the teacher-respondents toward disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) is highly positive, as indicated by a grand weighted mean of 4.69, which corresponds to "strongly agree." Among the specific aspects of DRRM, the teachers most strongly agreed (weighted mean of 4.77) with the statement that "DRRM is an important aspect of our education." While all aspects received strong agreement, the statement with the lowest weighted mean (4.61) was "DRRM enables our school to draw on other sources of knowledge regarding disaster risk reduction and management."

13. The teacher-respondents exhibit a strong sense of preparedness for natural disasters along with disaster risk reduction and management drill, as indicated by a grand weighted mean of 3.38, interpreted as "Very Well Prepared" in relation to disaster risk reduction and management drills. Among the specific indicators of readiness, the highest level of preparedness (weighted mean of 3.46) is associated with the statement "The office discusses what to do (before, during, and after a disaster)." While all aspects indicate a high level of preparedness, the statement with the lowest weighted mean (3.26) is "The office plans and prepares before a disaster risk reduction drill."

14. The teacher-respondents demonstrate a good level of readiness for natural disasters in terms of emergency evacuation, with a grand weighted mean of 3.18, interpreted as "Well Prepared." The aspect of emergency evacuation where teachers feel most prepared (weighted mean of 3.37, interpreted as "Very Well Prepared") is the office's discussion of the importance of knowing emergency evacuation procedures across various subject areas with employees. However, the distribution of evacuation maps to employees received the lowest weighted mean (2.93, interpreted as "Well Prepared"), indicating a slightly lower level of preparedness in this specific area compared to the overall readiness and the emphasis on discussing the importance of evacuation.

15. The teacher-respondents demonstrate a good level of readiness for natural disasters in terms of emergency response, with a grand weighted mean of 3.23, which is interpreted as "Well Prepared." The aspect of emergency response where teachers feel most prepared (weighted mean of 3.34, interpreted as "Very Well Prepared") is the office's performance of simulation exercises during earthquake drills. However, the integration of emergency response into various Local Government Unit (LGU) activities received the lowest weighted mean (3.16, interpreted as "Well Prepared"), indicating a slightly lower level of perceived readiness in this specific area compared to the overall emergency response preparedness and the practice of simulation exercises.

16. The survey findings indicated that five profile variates exhibited a statistically significant correlation with the level of readiness of teacher-respondents towards natural disasters. These variates were age, number of years in teaching, types of natural disasters experienced, frequency of exposure to natural disasters, and attitude toward disaster risk reduction and management. For each of these, the p-values were below the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that the observed correlations were unlikely due to chance. Specifically, age showed a weak positive correlation ($\rho=0.313$,

$p=0.001$), as did the number of years in teaching ($p=0.285$, $p=0.003$) and attitude toward disaster risk reduction and management ($p=0.372$, $p=0.000$). Conversely, both the types of natural disasters experienced ($p=-0.275$, $p=0.004$) and the frequency of exposure to natural disasters ($p=-0.254$, $p=0.008$) showed weak negative correlations with the level of readiness. Notably, despite the statistical significance, all five correlations were categorized as weak, suggesting that while these factors have some influence on teachers' preparedness, they are not strong predictors on their own.

17. The analysis of the remaining variables, including sex, gross monthly family income, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, grade level taught, relevant in-service trainings, and the number of School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (SDDRM) activities attended or participated, revealed no statistically significant correlation with the teacher-respondents' level of readiness for natural disasters. This indicates that these demographic and professional characteristics, as well as participation in relevant training and activities, did not significantly predict or influence the self-reported preparedness levels of the teachers in the face of natural calamities.

18. The teacher-respondents strongly agree with the immediate response strategies employed in the face of natural disasters, as indicated by a grand weighted mean of 3.39. Among these strategies, "Search and rescue operations" received the highest level of agreement (weighted mean of 3.46, interpreted as "strongly agree"). While all immediate response strategies garnered strong agreement, the "Provision of food" received the lowest weighted mean (3.33, interpreted as "strongly agree"), suggesting a slightly less strong agreement on this particular aspect compared to search and rescue efforts.

19. The teacher-respondents strongly agree with the short-term response strategies implemented in the face of natural disasters, as evidenced by a grand weighted mean of 3.47. Among these strategies, "Conducting mock drills / emergency drills" received the highest level of agreement (weighted mean of 3.60, interpreted as "strongly agreed"). While all short-term response strategies were met with strong agreement, "Disaster risk identification" received the lowest weighted mean (3.39, interpreted as "strongly agreed"), indicating a slightly less strong agreement on this specific aspect compared to the emphasis on conducting drills.

20. The teacher-respondents strongly agree with the protracted duration response strategies employed in the face of natural disasters, as indicated by a grand weighted mean of 3.43. Among these strategies, the "Adoption of disaster risk reduction drills" received the highest level of agreement (weighted mean of 3.50, interpreted as "strongly agreed"). While all protracted duration response strategies garnered strong agreement, "Disaster and risk assessment" received the lowest weighted mean (3.39, interpreted as "strongly agreed"), suggesting a slightly less strong agreement on this particular aspect compared to the adoption of drills.

21. The findings revealed that a statistically significant relationship existed

between teachers' attitudes toward disaster risk reduction and management and the response strategies they employed when facing natural disasters. With a p-value of 0.004, which was below the conventional significance level of 0.05, it was concluded that this observed correlation was unlikely to have occurred by chance. However, the Spearman's rho value of 0.275 suggested that while the correlation was significant, it was weak. This implied that although a teacher's positive or negative attitude towards disaster preparedness had some influence on their choice of response strategies, it was not a strong predictor.

22. The analysis of the survey data indicated that the remaining profile variates, including age, sex, gross monthly family income, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, grade level taught, number of years in teaching, relevant in-service trainings, number of School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (SDDRM) activities attended or participated, types of natural disasters experienced, and frequency of exposure to natural disasters, did not demonstrate a statistically significant correlation with the response strategies employed by the teacher-respondents when facing natural disasters.

23. The statistical analysis reveals a significant relationship between the response strategies employed by the teacher-respondents in the face of natural disasters and their perceived level of readiness across three key dimensions: disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) drill, emergency evacuation, and emergency response. The rejection of the null hypothesis, with computed p-values of 0.000 for all three dimensions (below the 0.05 significance level), confirms this significant association. Specifically, the strength of the relationship, as indicated by the Spearman rho values, is weak for DRRM drill (0.365) but moderate for both emergency evacuation (0.472) and emergency response (0.408).

24. The teacher-respondents find the preparation for natural disasters to be "Very Challenging" with respect to financial resources, as indicated by a grand weighted mean of 3.94. The most significant challenge identified (weighted mean of 4.00, interpreted as "Very Challenging") is the "Absence of financial donations from private institutions or entities." While all aspects related to financial resources are considered very challenging, the "Inadequate budget allocation for teachers' training on disaster preparedness from the schools' Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE)" is perceived as the least challenging among these (weighted mean of 3.82, interpreted as "Very Challenging").

25. The teacher-respondents perceive the challenges related to technology and equipment in preparing for natural disasters as "Very Challenging," with a grand weighted mean of 3.97. The most significant challenge identified (weighted mean of 4.10, interpreted as "Very Challenging") is the "Absence of technological tools to capture the extent of damage of natural disasters in schools, such as drones." While all aspects of technology and equipment are considered very challenging, the "Malfunctioning of gadgets for disaster risk reduction and management" is perceived as the least challenging among these (weighted mean of 3.86, interpreted as "Very Challenging").

26. The teacher-respondents find the challenges related to manpower in preparing for natural disasters to be "moderately challenging," with a grand weighted mean of 3.44. The most significant challenges identified (weighted means of 3.54, interpreted as "very challenging") are "Mismanaged manpower for disaster risk reduction and management in schools" and "Insufficient office for the school disaster risk reduction and management teams." In contrast, the "Absence of a sense of volunteerism among teachers in schools for disaster risk reduction and management" is perceived as the least challenging aspect of manpower (weighted mean of 3.32, interpreted as "moderately challenging").

27. The teacher-respondents find the challenges related to technical knowledge and understanding in preparing for natural disasters to be "moderately challenging," with a grand weighted mean of 3.38. The most significant challenge identified (weighted mean of 3.42, interpreted as "moderately challenging") is the "Lack of knowledge in disaster risk reduction and management by the teachers." While all aspects of technical knowledge and understanding are considered moderately challenging, the "Non-inclusion of disaster risk reduction and management in the curriculum" is perceived as the least challenging among these (weighted mean of 3.31, interpreted as "moderately challenging").

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The teacher-respondent demographic is predominantly female, married, and falls within a bimodal age range (27-31 and 42-46), with a significant portion earning P30,000-P34,999 monthly. Most teachers hold a Teacher III position, have some graduate units, and possess moderate teaching experience (6-15 years), often handling Grade 3, Kindergarten, or Grade 1. While school and district-level training is common, regional and national training are rarely attended. Teachers show a split in SDRRM activity participation, with many experiencing multiple natural disasters (especially flood, storm, and earthquake) repeatedly. Despite this, their overall attitude towards DRRM is overwhelmingly positive, recognizing its crucial role in education.

2. Teacher-respondents demonstrate a strong sense of preparedness for natural disasters and disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) drills, largely due to effective communication from their offices regarding actions to take before, during, and after a disaster. They also exhibit a good level of readiness for emergency evacuation, particularly in understanding its importance, though the distribution of evacuation maps could be improved. Similarly, their readiness for emergency response is good, with strong confidence in earthquake drill simulations, although there's room for improvement in integrating emergency response with broader Local Government Unit activities.

3. The study found that while several demographic and professional factors showed no significant correlation with teacher preparedness for natural disasters, age, number of years in teaching, types of natural disasters experienced, frequency of exposure to natural disasters, and attitude toward disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) all exhibited a statistically significant, although weak, correlation. Specifically, older teachers and those with more teaching experience, as well as those

with a positive attitude toward DRRM, tended to show slightly higher levels of readiness. Conversely, experiencing more types of disasters and more frequent exposure to them were weakly associated with a slightly lower level of readiness. These findings suggest that while these five factors play a role in preparedness, their individual influence is not substantial enough to be considered strong predictors.

4. The teacher-respondents demonstrate strong agreement with the effectiveness of various natural disaster response strategies, from immediate to protracted. They particularly endorse search and rescue operations for immediate response, conducting mock/emergency drills for short-term strategies, and the adoption of disaster risk reduction drills for long-term efforts. While all strategies received strong support, there was slightly less emphasis on food provision in immediate response and on disaster risk identification and disaster and risk assessment in short-term and protracted strategies, respectively. This suggests a general consensus on the importance of these measures, with a slight prioritization of active, hands-on preparedness and response over certain assessment and provision aspects.

5. The study revealed a statistically significant but weak positive correlation between teachers' attitudes toward disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) and the response strategies they employ during natural disasters. This means that while a teacher's attitude towards DRRM has some bearing on their chosen response, it isn't a dominant predictive factor. Conversely, a wide array of other teacher profile characteristics, including age, gender, income, civil status, education, teaching experience, position, grade level, and training attendance, showed no statistically significant relationship with the teachers' disaster response strategies. This suggests that for these teachers, personal DRRM attitude is a more influential factor in their disaster response than most demographic or professional attributes.

6. The study found a statistically significant relationship between the response strategies teachers employ during natural disasters and their perceived level of readiness across all three key dimensions: disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) drills, emergency evacuation, and emergency response. While the correlation was weak for DRRM drills, it was moderate for both emergency evacuation and emergency response. This suggests that teachers' chosen response strategies are indeed linked to how prepared they feel, with a stronger connection to their readiness for actual evacuations and emergency actions.

7. Teacher-respondents face significant challenges in preparing for natural disasters, particularly concerning financial resources and technology and equipment, both perceived as "Very Challenging." The most pressing financial hurdle is the absence of private donations, while the lack of technological tools like drones for damage assessment is the top technology concern. While still challenging, manpower and technical knowledge and understanding are considered "Moderately Challenging." Within manpower, mismanagement and insufficient office space are key issues, whereas for technical knowledge, the teachers' own lack of expertise stands out as the primary concern.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings, the following

recommendations are offered:

1. Targeted interventions considering age and teaching experience. Develop and implement tiered training programs that cater to the specific needs and potential knowledge gaps of teachers at different stages of their careers. Newer teachers may benefit from foundational knowledge and skills, while more experienced teachers could engage in advanced or refresher courses, focusing on new strategies and emerging threats.

2. Cultivating a proactive attitude towards DRRM. Integrate attitudinal components into training programs, emphasizing the importance of preparedness and its impact on safety. Leadership within schools can model and promote a culture of preparedness.

3. Addressing the impact of disaster experience and exposure. The weak negative correlations between the types and frequency of disaster exposure and readiness suggest that experiencing more disasters or frequent exposure does not automatically translate to greater preparedness. Develop support mechanisms and training that specifically address the potential for increased apprehension or feelings of inadequacy among teachers with more disaster experience. Focus on translating lessons learned into actionable preparedness strategies.

4. Comprehensive and regular DRRM training. A standardized and comprehensive DRRM training program is essential for all teachers, irrespective of their background. This training should cover various aspects of disaster preparedness, including risk assessment, early warning systems, evacuation procedures, first aid, and psychological support. Regular refresher courses and drills are crucial to reinforce learning and build confidence.

5. Strengthening school-based DRRM activities. Ensure that SDDRM activities are practical, engaging, and directly relevant to the specific hazards faced by the school and community in Hinabangan. Focus on active participation and skill-building rather than passive attendance.

6. Reinforcing the link between attitude and response. The significant, although weak, correlation between attitude toward DRRM and response strategies highlights the need to continue fostering a positive and informed attitude. Emphasize the importance of proactive engagement in DRRM for effective response during and after a disaster.

7. Exploring other factors influencing response. Since attitude alone is a weak predictor of response strategies, further investigation is needed to identify other significant factors influencing how teachers react during natural disasters in Hinabangan. This could include access to resources, clarity of emergency protocols, leadership during crises, communication systems, and the availability of mental health support.

8. Strengthening DRRM drills for enhanced response. The weak correlation between readiness in DRRM drills and actual response strategies suggests that current drill practices may need to be enhanced. Focus on the quality and realism of drills, ensuring they simulate potential disaster scenarios effectively and allow teachers to practice their roles and decision-making under pressure.

9. Prioritizing emergency evacuation preparedness. The moderate correlation between readiness in emergency evacuation and actual response underscores the importance of robust evacuation plans and regular, well-practiced drills. Ensure that all

teachers are thoroughly familiar with evacuation routes, assembly points, and procedures for accounting for all students.

10. Investing in emergency response skills. The moderate correlation between readiness in emergency response and actual response highlights the need for teachers to be equipped with practical emergency response skills, such as basic first aid, search and rescue procedures, and communication protocols. Provide accessible and relevant training in these areas.

11. Integrating readiness dimensions for comprehensive preparedness. The varying strengths of correlation between different dimensions of readiness and response suggest the need for a holistic approach to preparedness. Efforts should focus on improving readiness across all dimensions – DRRM drills, emergency evacuation, and emergency response – to ensure a more effective and coordinated response during natural disasters.

12. Future research should investigate other potential variables that may significantly influence teachers' readiness and response strategies. These could include personality traits, levels of self-efficacy, access to personal preparedness resources, community support networks, and the specific characteristics of the school environment. Also, to gain a deeper understanding of teachers' experiences, perceptions, and decision-making processes during natural disasters, future studies could incorporate qualitative research methods such as interviews, focus groups, and case studies. This can provide rich contextual data to complement quantitative findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The conduct of this study adhered strictly to ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, approval was obtained from the appropriate institutional review board, ensuring that all procedures met ethical standards. Informed consent was secured from all participating elementary teachers, who were fully briefed on the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty, and confidentiality of their responses was rigorously maintained. Data were collected and analyzed with utmost respect for privacy and integrity, ensuring that findings accurately reflect the participants' perspectives while upholding ethical research practices.

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